

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE EQUATIONS OF HÜCKEL AND SMOLUCHOWSKI CONNECTING ELECTROKINETIC POTENTIAL WITH THE CATAPHORETIC AND ELECTRO-ENDOSMOTIC VELOCITIES

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The electrokinetic potential of the particles of suspensions of hydrogen mica, sodium mica and sodium bentonite has been measured at the same concentration of electrolytes both by the cataphoretic and the electro-endosmotic methods. Calculated from the experimental data by using Smoluchowski's equation, the values of the electrokinetic potential measured by the endosmotic method agree well with those, measured by the cataphoretic method. It is therefore concluded that for the suspensions studied, Smoluchowski's equation is in better agreement with facts than Hückel's equation.

The electrokinetic potential plays a very important role in colloidal behaviour. The cataphoretic and the electro-osmotic methods are very commonly used for its measurement. Based on the theories of double layer of Helmholtz and Lamb, Smoluchowski deduced the following equations connecting the electrokinetic potential ξ with the cataphoretic velocity v of the colloidal particles or the electro-osmotic velocity u of the dispersion medium flowing through a diaphragm made of the colloidal particles :

$$\xi_E = \frac{4\pi\eta u}{DE} \quad (\text{for electro-osmosis})$$

$$\xi_C = \frac{4\pi\eta v}{DE} \quad (\text{for cataphoresis})$$

In the equations D represents the dielectric constant and η , the viscosity of the liquid, and E , the applied potential gradient.

Debye and Hückel (*Physikal. Z.*, 1924, 25, 49) have suggested that the cataphoretic mobility depends on the shape of the particles involved. For cylindrical particles and also for electro-osmotic flow through a capillary tube, Smoluchowski's formulae have been accepted by them as correct, but for the cataphoresis of spherical particles Hückel (*ibid.*, 1924, 25, 204) has deduced a formula in which 4π in Smoluchowski's equation has been replaced by 6π . A controversy has thus arisen as to which of these formulae represents facts correctly. According to Henry (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, A, 133, 106) the equation of Smoluchowski should hold good for particles whose radius is not less than 300 times the thickness of the double layer, while for very small particles of radius about 0.5 of the thickness of the double layer, Hückel's equation should hold good. Hermans (*Phil. Mag.*, 1938, 26, 659) has laid stress on the fact that in an electric field the relative motion of the particle and the liquid destroys the spherical symmetry of the ionic atmosphere and produces the so-called relaxation effect. From a detailed mathematical analysis Hermans (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, 35, 133) has concluded that

if $Ka > 1$, the ions in the double layer of the particle succeed in keeping pace with it in the electric field and the influence of the relaxation effect is small, being negligible at still higher values of Ka , where $1/K$ represents thickness of the double layer and a , the radius of the particle.

It has also been suggested by Bikerman (*J. chim. phys.*, 1935, 32, 285) that the Smoluchowski equation does not enable us to calculate the true values of electrokinetic potential owing to the existence of surface conduction. This effect, according to Overbeek and Wijga (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1946, 65, 556) becomes negligible at a concentration of the order of $2 \times 10^{-4} N$ of electrolytes such as KNO_3 .

It thus appears that most of the factors complicating the measurement of electrokinetic potential will be almost eliminated if one works with suspensions consisting of particles of fairly large size and with a relatively high concentration of the added electrolytes.

In this connection a considerable amount of work has already been done by Van der Grinten (*J. chim. phys.*, 1926, 23, 239), Bull and Gortner (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 111), Moyer and Abramson (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1936, 19, 727), Daniel (*ibid.*, 1932, 16, 457), Dummet and Bowden (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1933, A, 142, 382), Henry (*loc. cit.*), White, Monaghan and Urban (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, 39, 611), White and Monaghan (*ibid.*, 1935, 39, 925), White and Fourn (*ibid.*, 1938, 42, 29) and Ghosh and Roy (this *Journal*, 1939, 16, 634). The results obtained by these authors are mutually contradictory, some supporting Smoluchowski's equation, while others supporting Hückel's equation. All the workers with the exception of Ghosh and Roy (*loc. cit.*) and Van der Grinten (*loc. cit.*) used wax or protein to coat the surfaces of the micro-cataphoretic cell and of the particles, assuming that such coatings render the surface identical. In view of the fact that this assumption may not always hold good, we have used the particles of the same suspension without any coating to measure u and v in presence of known concentrations of electrolytes. The particles used were fairly large in size and the concentration of the added electrolyte was not lower than $1 \times 10^{-4} N$. The results obtained by using hydrogen mica, sodium mica and sodium bentonite systems are recorded in Tables I, II and III.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Sodium Bentonite.—Crude bentonite (from Kashmir) was shaken with $N/2$ -NaOH solution, allowed to settle for 8 hours in a tall jar, and 10 cm. from its upper portion was siphoned off. The process was repeated several times and thus clay particles of size 2×10^{-5} cm. and lower were separated from still larger particles. The clay suspension was acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitate washed repeatedly with dilute HCl

solution to ensure complete replacement of Na^+ by H^+ . The acid bentonite was washed several times with distilled water by decantation and then treated with hydrogen peroxide to oxidise the organic matter it contained. The excess of H_2O_2 was removed by gentle heating and the precipitate was subjected to electro-dialysis till the electric current became very low and constant. The electro-dialysed material was then suspended in conductivity water in a Jena glass bottle and its bentonite content estimated. The base-exchange capacity of the suspension was determined by the barium acetate method and the requisite quantity of NaOH was added to convert the hydrogen bentonite into sodium bentonite. The suspension was then diluted with conductivity water to a bentonite content of 1%. The suspension was kept in a well stoppered Jena glass bottle.

Preparation of Hydrogen Mica and Sodium Mica.—Sheet mica (Muscovite) was cut into small pieces, ground in an electric machine to a fine powder and suspended in water in a tall jar. The particles of the size of 2×10^{-5} cm. or lower were separated as in the case of bentonite. The material after treatment first with HCl and then with H_2O_2 was subjected to electro-dialysis. The base-exchange capacity of the hydrogen mica thus obtained was determined and by adding the calculated quantity of NaOH to a given quantity of the hydrogen mica, it was converted into sodium mica. The hydrogen mica and the sodium mica suspensions were then stored separately in well stoppered Jena bottles.

Cataphoretic and Electro-endosmotic Measurements

The cataphoretic velocity of the suspended particles was determined by using a flat rectangular micro-cataphoretic cell of the same type as was used by Freundlich and Abramson (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 128, 25). The velocity of the particles was usually determined at $0.21/d$ (d represents the depth of the cell) from the lower surface of the top plate and frequently checked by comparison with the value calculated from measurements of velocities at $d/2$ and $d/6$, using the equation,

$$V = \left(\frac{3}{4}v_1 + \frac{1}{4}v_2\right)$$

where v_1 and v_2 represent the observed velocities at $d/6$ and $d/2$ respectively. The micro-cataphoretic cell was always filled with a mixture consisting of the desired electrolyte and the suspension mixed in equal proportion by volume. The other experimental details were the same as described in a previous paper by Ghosh and Roy (*loc. cit.*).

In the electro-endosmotic measurements the arrangement used was the same as described in the previous paper by Ghosh and Roy (*loc. cit.*). The suspension and the electrolyte were mixed in equal proportion by volume and the mixture centrifuged for a while. The supernatant solution was carefully poured into a beaker and the precipitate with a little of the supernatant solution was transferred to the U-tube. The U-tube was then put in a bag

and centrifuged for a definite period of time to form the diaphragm. The rest of the procedure was the same as described in a previous paper by Ghosh and Roy (*loc. cit.*). The values of electrokinetic potential recorded in the following tables have been calculated by using Smoluchowski's equation and taking $D=80$ and $\eta=0.00839$.

TABLE I
Electro-endosmotic measurements.

Normality of the electrolyte in the suspension.	Sp. conduc.	Current (i).	Electro-endosmotic velocity.	ξ_E .
		Hydrogen mica.		
0.001 NaCl	0.000112 mhos	0.000265 amp.	0.000419 (c.c./sec)	0.021 volt
0.0013 NaNO ₃	0.000145	0.000314	0.000437	0.024
0.003 Na ₂ SO ₄	0.000302	0.000624	0.000438	0.025
0.0002 BaCl ₂	0.0000576	0.0000605	0.000097	0.011
0.0001 Th(NO ₃) ₄	0.0000384	0.00009	0.000264	0.013
		Sodium mica.		
0.075 KCl	0.01013	0.017	0.000389	0.027
0.0025 BaCl ₂	0.000382	0.0035	0.002044	0.026
0.00113 Th(NO ₃) ₄	0.000209	0.001	0.00038	0.010
		Sodium bentonite.		
0.0188 KCl	0.00262	0.017	0.0012	0.022
0.0055 BaCl ₂	0.000616	0.00342	0.000957	0.021
0.00225 AlCl ₃	0.000302	0.000603	0.000459	0.027 ^a
0.0025 T(NO ₃) ₄	0.000353	0.0008	0.000481	0.025

TABLE II
Cataphoretic measurements.

Normality of the electrolyte in the suspension.	Sp. conduc.	Current (i)	Velocity	ξ_E .
		Hydrogen mica.	(cm./volt./per sec. $\times 10^{-5}$.)	
0.001 NaCl	0.000112 mho	0.000049 amp.	20.0	0.024 volt
0.0013 NaNO ₃	0.000145	0.000062	21.0	0.025
0.003 Na ₂ SO ₄	0.000302	0.00012	20.6	0.024
0.0002 BaCl ₂	0.0000576	0.000029	9.6	0.011
0.0001 Th(NO ₃) ₄	0.0000384	0.0000183	10.6	0.013
		Sodium mica.		
0.075 KCl	0.01013	0.01	25.3	0.030
0.0025 BaCl ₂	0.000382	0.00049	24.8	0.029
0.00113 Th(NO ₃) ₄	0.000209	0.00175	9.0	0.011
		Sodium bentonite.		
0.0188 KCl	0.00262	0.00113	18.4	0.022
0.0055 BaCl ₂	0.000616	0.000383	16.8	0.020
0.00225 AlCl ₃	0.000302	0.000125	23.3	0.028
0.0025 Th(NO ₃) ₄	0.000353	0.00013	22.2	0.026

TABLE III

Normality of the electrolyte in the suspension.	ξ_E .	ξ_C .	Ratio of ξ_C/ξ_E .
Hydrogen mica suspension.			
0.001 NaCl	0.021 volt	0.024 volt	1.14
0.0013 NaNO ₃	0.024	0.025	1.04
0.003 Na ₂ SO ₄	0.025	0.024	0.96
0.0002 BaCl ₂	0.011	0.011	1.00
0.0001 Th(NO ₃) ₄	0.013	0.013	1.00
Sodium mica suspension.			
0.075 KCl	0.027	0.030	1.11
0.0025 BaCl ₂	0.026	0.029	1.12
0.00113 Th(NO ₃) ₄	0.010	0.011	1.10
Sodium bentonite suspension.			
0.0188 KCl	0.022	0.022	1.00
0.0055 BaCl ₂	0.021	0.020	0.95
0.00225 AlCl ₃	0.027	0.028	1.04
0.0025 Th(NO ₃) ₄	0.025	0.026	1.04
			Average 1.04

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Tables I and II that for the three suspensions, sodium bentonite, hydrogen mica and sodium mica, suitable concentrations of different electrolytes have been ascertained at which the electrokinetic potential of the particles could be measured by both the electroendosmotic and the cataphoretic methods. The values of ξ_E and ξ_C calculated from the experimental data by using Smoluchowski's equation have been recorded in Table III. It will be evident from this table that they agree well with each other for any given suspension at the same concentration of a particular electrolyte. The ratio of ξ_C/ξ_E does not differ much from unity and average of all the values is 1.04. These results therefore justify our drawing the conclusion that for the three suspensions mentioned above, Smoluchowski's equation is in better agreement with the observed facts than Hückel's equation.